

TPI EFFECT ON RESIN IMPREGNATION IN VARTM AND ITS MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Nowadays, natural fiber reinforced composites are expected as structural materials, and already applied to industrial products such as car interior parts and electrical products [1]. Natural fiber made from plants mainly consists of cellulose, which has a high elastic modulus of 138GPa in its crystal part [2]. Then it is expected that the natural fiber will widely be substituted for conventional glass fibers. The research and development of materials using the biomass sources provide opportunity for a sustainable society.

It is known that a single yarn is formed by spinning natural short fibers and a twist yarn consists of some single yarns in order to achieve high stiffness and strength of natural fiber composites. Generally, it is found that the amount of twist obtained by the spinning process, called twist per inch (TPI), plays an important role in yarn properties because the twist is essential to hold the fibers together [3]. In fact, twisted yarns are normally used for increasing the lateral cohesion of the filaments and also for ease of handling. By twisting yarns, possible micro damages within the yarn can be localized, leading to possible increase in the failure strength of the yarn [4].

Meanwhile, the application of liquid composite molding processes, such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and resin infusion also known as Vacuum assisted RTM (VaRTM) has grown tremendously in recent years [5-12]. VaRTM allows the fabrication of composite parts with high fiber volume content and good laminate and part quality at reduced costs compared to classical autoclave processes. However,

very little research has been done on the use of RTM and VaRTM in making natural fiber polymer composites [13, 14]. The trend of using RTM to make natural fiber composites is beginning to grow due to the short cycle time and automation-friendliness of the process that lends itself particularly well for use in the high volume automotive sector [15, 16]. In any RTM process, complete filling of the mold with adequate wetting of fibers is the mold designer's primary objective. Incomplete filling in the mold leads to production of defective parts with dry spots [6, 7, 11, 17, 18]. It is also important for the mold designer to minimize fill-time and fluid pressure buildup during the filling process to make the technology cost-effective in a manufacturing environment.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on resin impregnation properties, such as flow velocity and void generation, and its mechanical properties for natural fiber composite molded by VaRTM. Furthermore, a novel VaRTM method of natural fiber composites based on the TPI dependence on the resin impregnation properties was proposed. Finally, the VaRTM applications using the present method were also demonstrated. Moreover, the tensile properties and fracture mechanism of the particular parallel laminates using various TPI yarns for actual applications were investigated.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials and testing

The reinforcement used in this study was a ramie single yarn (No.16, supplied by TOSCO, CO., Ltd). Five-twisted yarns were produced from ramie single yarns using a twisting machine (Mini Twister AMT-2W, Marui Textile Machinery Co., Ltd.). The numbers of twists (TPI) prepared were 1.5, 3.5, 6.5 and 9.5 /inch. The bio-based thermosetting resin, acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO), Ebecryl 860 produced by Daicel-Cytec Co., Ltd, was used as matrix for VaRTM. This composite is fully bio-based composites. The hardeners for resin were a t-butyl peroxybenzoate produced by Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. or a Dibenzoyl peroxide CH-50L produced by Kayaku Akzo corporation.

The VaRTM outline was shown in Fig.1. 5 yarns with various TPIs for measuring the flow velocity of resin and twelve yarns for testing to obtain the mechanical properties were arranged in one direction. Then, the unidirectional natural yarn composites were molded using VaRTM. Specimens for tensile tests had 90mm gauge length, a width of 15mm and an average thickness of 2mm. The tensile test speed was 1mm/min. Hereafter, the name of composites specimen with 1.5~9.5 TPI yarns were abbreviated as AR1.5~9.5, respectively. The number of specimens was five for all cases.

Fig.1 VaRTM outline and resin flow

2.2 Resin impregnation properties

The schematic of resin flow in VaRTM after 4 minutes and the flow velocities of resin were also shown in Fig.1 and Table 1, respectively. Here, v is the flow velocity of resin. It was found that the resin flow velocity increases with increasing TPI because the capillary pressure due to the dense structure of fibers becomes the predominant force for tow impregnation. The capillary pressures P_{cap} and the yarn permeability K_i of yarns with various TPI were also shown in Table 1. The capillary pressure was calculated by

$$P_{cap} = \frac{2\gamma \cos \theta}{r_i} \quad (1)$$

where, γ is the resin surface tension, θ is the contact angle between resin and fibers and r_i is the capillary radius. The permeability derived from Darcy's law was given by

$$K_i = \frac{v\mu l}{\Delta p + P_{cap}} \quad (2)$$

where, μ is the resin viscosity, Δp is the fluid pressure difference over the flow distance in the yarns l . These material properties were shown in Table 2. From the view point of Darcy's law, it was found that the flow velocity in the yarns with high TPI increases due to the high permeability.

The cross-section photographs using a laser microscope for AR1.5 and 9.5 were shown in Fig.2. Five yarns in AR9.5 composites closely approached each other, on the other hands five yarns in AR1.5 separated. Because the capillary pressure between yarns was lower than that in yarn [12], the flow velocity with low TPI became a low level. More large magnification photographs in one yarn were presented in Fig.3. It was confirmed that there is no void in the case of all TPI. Consequently, it was cleared that the resin impregnation using present method was fine.

Table 1 Impregnation and tensile properties

	Neat	AR1.5	AR3.5	AR6.5	AR9.5
v [mm/s]	-	0.55	0.64	0.73	0.85
r_i [mm]	-	7.6×10^{-6}	6.8×10^{-6}	6.3×10^{-6}	5.9×10^{-6}
P_{cap} [kPa]	-	8.6	9.6	10.4	11.1
K_i [m ²]	-	3.3×10^{-8}	3.5×10^{-8}	3.7×10^{-8}	4.0×10^{-8}
σ [MPa]	11.4	141.1	102.9	74.0	55.6
E [GPa]	0.73	14.3	7.81	5.33	3.93
ε_f [%]	3.32	1.60	2.33	2.72	2.74

Table 2 Material properties for calculations

Resin surface tension, γ [N/m]	0.05
Contact angle, θ [°]	49
Resin viscosity, μ [Pa·s]	3.5
Fluid pressure, Δp [Pa]	100
Flow distance, l [m]	0.15

(a) AR1.5

(b) AR9.5

Fig.2 Cross-section observations for five yarns

(a) AR1.5

(b) AR9.5

Fig.3 Cross-section observations in yarn

2.3 Mechanical properties

The yarn TPI dependence on the stress-strain relation for natural fiber composite was shown in Fig.4. The obtained tensile properties were also denoted in Table 1. In Table 1, σ is the tensile strength, E is the Young's modulus and ε_f is the fracture strain. The tensile strength and Young's modulus increase with decreasing TPI, while the

fracture strain increases with increasing TPI because the mechanical properties depends on the twist angles [3].

Fig.4 Stress-strain relations

3 VaRTM applications

3.1 Resin flow control in VaRTM

In the case of actual application of structures molded by VaRTM, the complicated structures with corner, curved surface and branch and merge of resin paths existed. At such change point of resin flow velocities, it was concerned that the insufficient impregnation of resin into yarns easily occurred [8]. In this section, some applications using present VaRTM method were introduced.

One of the application examples of resin flow control for design of natural fiber composite structures molded by presented VaRTM was shown in Fig.5-(a). Two resin paths with corner were prepared. On one hand twelve yarns with 1.5 TPI were arranged and on the other hand three yarns with four kinds of TPis were arranged. In fact, at the inner side three yarns with 1.5 TPI were arranged, those with 3.5 and 6.5 TPI which have higher flow velocities followed to them and at the outer side those with 9.5 TPI were finally arranged so that the resin flow detour in the corner based on the difference of flow velocities.

The schematic of resin flow in VaRTM after five minutes was also shown in Fig.5-(b). It was found that the resin detoured near corner in the latter case. Consequently, the void occurrence due to the resin

flow path near corners was prevented as much as possible owing to arrange the yarns with various TPis.

(a) Overview of VaRTM

(b) Schematic of resin flow

Fig.5 Resin flow control application example

3.2 Resin flow acceleration in VaRTM

One of the application examples of resin flow acceleration for design of natural fiber composite structures molded by presented VaRTM was shown in Fig.6-(a). At first two twelve yarns with 1.5 TPI were prepared. These are with and without an acceleration path using two yarns with 9.5 TPI which have higher flow velocities. The acceleration path put on the twelve yarns with 1.5 TPI.

The schematic of resin flow in VaRTM after five minutes was also shown in Fig.6-(b). It was found that the resin impregnation accelerated in the latter case. Consequently, in the case of a large structure with branch and merge resin path, the void occurrence due to the resin impregnation lag was prevented as much as possible owing to add the acceleration path with high TPI.

(a) Overview of VaRTM

(b) Schematic of resin flow

Fig.6 Resin flow acceleration application example

4 Tensile properties of various ‘parallel lamina’

4.1 Various ‘parallel laminae’ preparation

It was cleared that the void occurrence can be prevented as much as possible when the yarns with various TPIs are arranged in parallel. However, the tensile properties depend on the TPI, as shown in

Fig.4. We called the composites with various TPIs as a parallel lamina. Then, the tensile properties of various parallel laminae as shown in Fig.7 should be investigated.

Three kinds of parallel lamina were prepared as shown in Table 3. The number of yarns was three each other. AR1369 was arranged in order as the application example shown in Fig.5. AR1963 has the low fracture strain lines of 1.5 and 3.5 TPIs at outside lines. On the other hand, AR6139 has the low fracture strain lines at inside lines. The unidirectional parallel laminae were molded using VaRTM. Specimens for tensile tests had 90mm gauge length, a width of 15mm and an average thickness of 2mm. The tensile test speed was 1mm/min. The number of specimens was five for all cases.

Fig.7 Tensile specimen with various TPI yarns

Table 3 Parallel laminae

Abbreviation	AR1369	AR1963	AR6139
1 st line	1.5 TPI	1.5 TPI	6.5 TPI
2 nd line	3.5 TPI	9.5 TPI	1.5 TPI
3 rd line	6.5 TPI	6.5 TPI	3.5 TPI
4 th line	9.5 TPI	3.5 TPI	9.5 TPI

4.2 Tensile properties

Fig.8 shows the stress-strain relations for various parallel laminae. The obtained tensile properties were shown in Table 4. The Young’s modulus of all laminae were predicted using a law of mixture as follows,

$$E_c = \sum E_{AR,i} V_i + E_m V_m \quad (3)$$

where, $E_{AR,i}$ is the Young’s modulus of i TPI line and V_i is the volume fraction of i TPI line. E_m and V_m are

the Young's modulus and volume fraction of resin, respectively. The predictions of Young's modulus were good agreement with experimental modulus.

The tensile bundle strength σ/V_f and the normalized Young's modulus E/V_f of AR6139 were higher than those of AR1369 and AR1963. It was found that the arrangement of low TPI lines to inside bring the high tensile strength for the parallel laminae. The knee point in the stress-strain relation of AR1963 occurred. It was found from the in-situ observation that this knee point derived from the fracture of 1.5 TPI lines. Moreover, the fracture strains of AR1369, 1963 and 6139 were lower than 2.0%. In Table 1, the fracture strains of AR3.5, 6.5 and 9.5 were higher than 2.0%. Consequently, it was indicated that the whole final failure of parallel laminae was controlled by the failure of 1.5 TPI line.

Fig.8 Stress-strain relations for parallel laminae

Table 4 Tensile properties for parallel laminae

	AR1369	AR1963	AR6139
Volume fraction V_f [%]	27.6	27.2	31.0
Tensile strength σ [MPa]	74.2	74.6	94.3
Young's modulus E [GPa]	7.76	7.51	8.71
Fracture strain [%]	1.61	1.64	1.78
σ/V_f	268.0	273.7	303.9
E/V_f	28.1	27.7	28.2
E prediction [GPa]	8.32	7.92	8.38

4.3 Fracture aspects

Fig.9 shows the photograph of scanning electron microscope for the 1.5 and 9.5 TPI lines of AR1963 specimen. The fracture surface of 3.5 TPI line appeared similar to 1.5 TPI line and that of 6.5 TPI line was similar to 9.5 TPI line. The fracture surface of 1.5 TPI line was approximately flat and that of 9.5 TPI line was roughness due to pull-out fracture of twist yarns. It was considered that this pull-out fracture of twist yarns brought the high fracture strain. However, the stress concentration owing to the crack of 1.5 TPI lines was enough large to cause the whole final failure of parallel laminae.

(a) TPI=1.5

(b) TPI=9.5

Fig.9 SEM photographs of AR1963

5 Conclusions

The unidirectional natural fiber composites with twist yarns were molded by VaRTM. The twist yarns used in this study have four kinds of twist per inch (TPI) such as 1.5, 3.5, 6.5 and 9.5. The twist angle, the dense of yarns and the distance between yarns depends on the TPI of yarns. Then, the resin impregnation properties in VaRTM and its mechanical properties were investigated in this study. The following conclusions were derived.

1. In the case of various TPIs composites for the present study, there is no void in the yarns, so the VaRTM was applicable to mold the structures for the natural fiber composites. Additionally, the resin flow velocity increases with increasing TPI because the capillary pressure due to the dense structure of fibers becomes the predominant force for tow impregnation. That is, the resin flow velocity in yarns depended on TPI of yarns.
2. The mechanical properties also depended heavily on TPI of yarns. The tensile strength and Young's modulus increase with decreasing TPI, while the fracture strain increases with increasing TPI because the mechanical properties depends on the twist angles.
3. The TPI dependence on the resin flow velocities was valuable to design the natural fiber composite structure with a corner and branch-merge yarns molded by VaRTM. The application examples of resin flow control and acceleration for design of natural fiber composite VaRTM structures were demonstrated. Consequently, the void occurrence due to the resin impregnation lag was prevented as much as possible owing to arrange the TPI of yarns.
4. The tensile properties of various parallel laminae using some kinds of TPI yarns were investigated. Consequently, it was indicated that the whole final failure under tensile loading of parallel laminae was controlled by the failure of 1.5 TPI line. It

was found that the arrangement of low TPI lines to inside bring the high tensile strength for the parallel laminae.

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